

**EVALUATION OF SAFETY DEVICES IN PUBLIC BUILDINGS IN OWERRI,
NIGERIA.**

BY

ONYEKWERE PATRICK .E.

16/37772

AND

OMEIKE SOCHUKWU .G.

16/34175

**FACULTY OF ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE,
IMO STATE UNIVERSITY, OWERRI.**

NOVEMBER 2022.

**EVALUATION OF SAFETY DEVICES IN PUBLIC BUILDINGS IN OWERRI,
NIGERIA.**

BY

ONYEKWERE PATRICK .E.

16/37772

and

OMEIKE SOCHUKWU .G.

16/34175

**A RESEARCH WORK SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
ARCHITECTURE, FACULTY OF ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES, IMO STATE
UNIVERSITY, OWERRI.**

**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT FOR THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCE
IN ARCHITECTURE**

NOVEMBER 2022.

DECLARATION

We hereby declare that this research work on evaluation of safety devices in public buildings in Owerri, Nigeria is a product of my efforts, under the supervision of Arc. Prof. M.U Okafor and Arc. R. K Nwokocha and has not been presented elsewhere for the award of Bachelor of Science Degree in Architecture. All sources have been duly distinguished and appropriately acknowledged.

Sign..... Date

Onyekwere Patrick .E.

16/37772

Sign..... Date

Omeike Sochukwu .G

16/34175

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the research work for this project and the subsequent preparation of the project by ONYEKWERE PATRICK E. with matric number 16/37772 and OMEIKE SOCHUKWU G. with matric number 16/ 34175 in the Department of Architecture were carried out under our supervision.

Name	Sign	Date
Arc R. K Nwokocha (Supervisor)
Arc L. O Asikogu (Head of Department)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Our acknowledgement goes to God Almighty, and to my supervisors, Arc Prof. M.U Okafor, Arc. R. K Nwokocha. To my family members, I will like to thank them for their wonderful support, care, understanding, encouragement and prayers.

We shall not fail to acknowledge the H.O.D. Department of Architecture Imo State University, and all the lecturers for the role they played in my life all through my years of study in the department.

Thanks to our friends and course mates in school for their continual encouragement and critics which has greatly helped in revealing my flops even on this research work.

DEDICATION

This project report is dedicated to Almighty God who has made everything possible for us towards achieving this project.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

COVER PAGE.....	i
TITLE PAGE	ii
DECLARATION.....	iii
CERTIFICATION	iv
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	v
DEDICATION.....	vi
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vii
LIST OF FIGURES.....	xi
LIST OF TABLES.....	xii
LIST OF PLATES	xiii
ABSTRACT.....	xv
CHAPTER ONE.....	1
1.0 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY	1
1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM	3
1.3 AIMS	4
1.4 OBJECTIVES	4

1.5	RESEARCH QUESTION.....	5
1.6	JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY	5
1.7	THE STUDY AREA.....	5
1.8	SCOPE OF THE STUDY	5
1.9	SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY.....	6
1.10	LIMITATION OF STUDY.....	6
	CHAPTER TWO.....	7
2.0	LITERATURE REVIEW.....	7
2.1	CONCEPTUAL LITERATURE.....	7
2.1.1	SAFETY DEVICES.....	10
2.1.2	BUILDING MAINTENANCE.....	18
2.1.3	MAINTENANCE AND SAFTY OF PUBLIC BUILDINGS.....	18
2.1.4	EMPIRICAL LITERATURE.....	19
	CHAPTER THREE.....	22
3.0	RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	22
3.1	PREVIEW.....	22
3.2	RESEARCH DESIGN... ..	22
3.3	SAMPLING.....	23

3.3.1	POPULATION	23
3.3.2	SAMPLING FRAME.....	24
3.3.3	SAMPLING METHOD.....	25
3.3.4	SAMPLING SIZE.....	25
3.4	METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION	25
3.5	AREA OF STUDY.....	26
3.6	DATA COLLECTION AND PROCESSING	27
3.7	METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS.....	27
	CHAPTER FOUR.....	28
4.0	DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS	28
4.1	DATA ON IMO STATE UNIVERCITY LIBRARY.....	29
4.1.1	EQUIPMENT AVAILABLE IN THE BUILDING.....	29
4.1.2	CONDITIONS OF THE AVAILABLE EQUIPMENT.....	31
4.2	DATA ON IMO STATE INTERNAL REVENUE SERVICE.....	32
4.2.1	EQUIPMENT AVAILABLE IN THE BUILDING.....	33
4.2.2	CONDITIONS OF THE AVAILABLE EQUIPMENT.....	34
4.3	DATA ON CATOL CATHEDRAL CHURCH.....	36
4.3.1	EQUIPMENT AVAILABLE IN THE BUILDING.....	36

4.3.2	CONDITIONS OF AVAILABLE EQUIPMENT.....	38
4.4	RESEARCH QUESTION 1.....	39
4.5	RESEARCH QUESTION 2.....	41
4.6	RESEARCH QUESTION 3.....	43
4.7	RESEARCH QUESTION 4.....	45
CHAPTER FIVE.....		47
5.0	CONCLUSION AND SUMMARY OF STUDY	47
5.1	DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS	47
5.2	IMPLICATIONS	48
5.3	LIMITATIONS OF STUDY.....	48
5.4	CONCLUSION AND SUMMARY OF THE STUDY	49
5.5	RECOMMENDATIONS.....	50
5.6	SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTHER STUDIES.....	50
REFERENCE.....		51

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 4.1.1(a): Showing equipment available in the building.....	30
Figure 4.1.1(b): Showing equipment available in the building.....	31
Figure 4.2.1(a): Showing equipment available in the building.....	33
Figure 4.2.1(b): Showing equipment available in the building.....	34
Figure 4.3.1(a): Showing equipment available in the building.....	37
Figure 4.3.1(b): Showing equipment available in the building.....	37
Figure 4.4: Showing the results and responses on the level of safety devices in Owerri.....	40
Figure 4.5(a): Showing conditions of the safety equipment in the building.....	42
Figure 4.5(b): Showing conditions of the safety equipment in the building.....	42
Figure 4.6(a): Showing the results and responses on the adequacy of the necessary devices.....	44
Figure 4.6(b): Showing the results and responses on the adequacy of the necessary devices.....	44
Figure 4.7(a): Showing the results and responses on the construction experts involving the services of the professionals.....	46
Figure 4.7(b): Showing the results and responses on the construction experts involving the services of the professionals.....	46

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.3.1 showing the building type and number of spaces.....	24
Table 4.1.1 showing equipment available in the building.....	29
Table 4.1.2 showing condition of available equipment.....	31
Table 4.2.1(a) showing equipment available in the building.....	33
Table 4.2.1(b) showing equipment available in the building.....	34
Table 4.2.2 showing condition of available equipment.....	34
Table 4.3.1 showing equipment available in the building.....	36
Table 4.3.2 showing condition of available equipment.....	38
Table 4.4: Showing the results and responses on the level of safety devices in Owerri.....	39
Table 4.5: Showing conditions of the safety equipment in the building.....	41
Table 4.6: Showing the results and responses on the adequacy of the necessary devices.....	43
Table 4.7: Showing the results and responses on the construction experts involving the services of the professionals.....	45

LIST OF PLATES

Plate 2.1.1(a): Showing Examples of some safety devices.....	10
plate 2.1.1(b): showing Fire extinguisher types and uses for different classifications of fire..	11
plate 2.1.1(c): Showing powder fire extinguisher.....	11
plate 2.1.1(d): Showing fire bucket.....	12
plate 2.1.1(e): Showing security cameras.....	13
plate 2.1.1(f): Showing smoke detector.....	14
plate 2.1.1(g): Showing fire exit door.....	14
plate 2.1.1(h): Showing loudspeaker.....	15
plate 2.1.1(i): Showing types of signages.....	16
plate 2.1.1(j): Showing tactile surfaces.....	17
Plate 2.1.1(k): Showing Building security and control systems.....	17
Plate 3.5: Showing map of Imo state indicating Owerri north.....	26
Plate 4.0: Showing location of the study area circled in red as indicated.....	28
Plate 4.1(a): Showing Imo state university library.....	29
Plate 4.1.2(a): Showing Imo state university library.....	31
Plate 4.1.2(b): Showing Imo state university library.....	32
Plate 4.2: Showing Imo internal revenue service.....	32
Plate 4.2.2(a): Showing Imo state internal revenue service.....	35
Plate 4.2.2(b): Showing Imo state internal revenue service.....	35
Plate 4.3: Showing catol cathedral church Anglican communion.....	36

Plate 4.3.2(a): Showing catol cathedral church Anglican communion.....38

Plate 4.3.2(b): Showing catol cathedral church Anglican communion.....39

ABSTRACT

The study evaluated safety devices in public buildings in Owerri, Nigeria. Both the qualitative and quantitative method of data collection was utilized. The study adopted the purposive sampling technique in selecting the sample. 50 questionnaires were distributed while 42 were returned. The Statistical software SPSS was used to analyzing the responses obtained from the respondents and descriptive statistics were provided. From the results of the analysis, it was discovered that a greater number of the respondents were of the opinion that the level of safety devices in public buildings in Owerri were fair. Also, construction engineers often engaged the services of safety professionals in the construction of buildings. The study concluded by pointing to the fact that emphasis in design of public buildings should be placed on durability and safety which would be achieved by installing safety devices. It also concluded that the services of safety experts should be engaged by construction engineers to bring in their knowledge as to what safety devices to install, how much of it that would be in place and the steps to take in maintaining and taking care of them. It recommended that buildings should be properly oriented before design and safety devices should be effectively and adequately installed. Also, Fire escapes and other alternatives to leaving the building in case of any emergency should never be left out in any public building.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

A building is regarded as an enclosure or “envelope” designed and constructed to provide minimum level of comfort, and conveniences for man. Cities depend on public services to function optimally. Public services are provided in public buildings, and good public buildings make it easier to deliver services to the community. Efficient delivery of public services can improve livability of cities, as they keep the cities running smoothly and effectively (Litman, 2015). The types of services provided in public buildings make it imperative that the buildings be fit for purpose, so as to accommodate large volumes of users and also withstand the expected wear and tear as a result of use. Expectedly, huge budgetary allocations are expended in erecting public buildings, and they should therefore remain in good enough condition for a long period of time, to justify the expenditure. Building provides safety, protects human inhabitants, animals and equipment from effects of weather, and gives internal comfort (Ogunoh, 2014). This implies that the primary purpose of buildings is to provide occupants with conducive, safe, comfortable, healthy and secured indoor environment to carry out different kinds of activities ranging from work, study, leisure and family life to social interactions.

In order to achieve this purpose, buildings are designed, planned, constructed and managed based on standards and specifications established by governments, professional bodies and experts who are supposed to have adequate knowledge of users’ needs and expectations. Studies such as Kaitilla, (1993); Ukoha and Beamish, 1997; Zeiler and Boxem, 2008; Meir, Garb, Jiao and Cicelsky, 2009; Eziyi, Akunnay, Albert and Dolapo (2013) have however shown that sometimes these standards and specifications do not conform to the changing needs and expectations of users; and thus, users are not always satisfied with the performance

of their buildings. The main functional requirement of building is to ensure strength and stability, weather tightness, internal comfort level, optimum use of buildings and a longer serviceable life of buildings.

Safety devices are pieces of equipment such as fire extinguishers, safety belts, burglar alarm, CCTV, access controls, etc. that reduces loss or damage from fire, accident or break-in.

The operation of public buildings, especially modern ones use control systems that connect to a vast array of devices and sensors. These sensors can be used to monitor pertinent information for daily operation as well as emergency scenarios. For the purposes of emergency response, there needs to be a standards-based framework for public safety officials and constructors of public buildings to ensure that all required and appropriate safety devices including; fire safety protections, communication systems (digital signages, tactile surfaces etc.), access control are installed in the building. The existence of monitor building automation system (BAS) generated alerts is vital. However, there is no standard method to enable this information transfer. This lack of a cohesive set of standards hinders the delivery of mission-critical data into the hands of public safety officials, and hinders the development of tools and methods that could use this data to improve the performance and safety of first responders in addressing emergency building incidents.

To date, there are many building automation systems using proprietary monitoring methods which hinder sensor integration within the building. Therefore, from the building itself, there is a challenge to gather building incident (emergency alert) data.

1.2 Statement of Problem

Over the years, public buildings in Owerri, south-east Nigeria have little or no safety devices installed in them. Many of these buildings have remained in such conditions for several years. Even in their states of lack of safety devices, the buildings remain actively in use, playing host to large numbers of people who work, and access services provided within them daily. As a result, large numbers of the urban population in Owerri are daily constrained to accept poor quality environments as normal. This expectedly has impacted negatively on the people, especially in view of the role quality of public buildings play in predicting neighborhood satisfaction (McCrea, Stimson & Western, 2005), and their further implications for social interactions and neighborhood crime (Couch & Dennemann, 2000). This is particularly a cause for concern as poor quality public buildings eventually transform into poor quality urban environments, further creating the possibility of slum development. The United Nation's Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11 underscores the critical importance of sustainable cities and communities in the quest to end poverty, protect the climate, and ensure the enjoyment of peace and prosperity by all people. Sustainable cities and communities can only come about by significantly transforming the way urban spaces are built and managed. Public buildings are a significant component of the urban space and must be seen to be properly planned and managed, so as to foster social, cultural and economic growth in the communities where they are.

In Owerri, as with Nigeria generally, there is a tendency towards constructing buildings without installing the necessary safety devices in them in a bid to reduce theft, accidents, injuries and disasters. One clear evidence of this, is the common and preventable accidents that occur in public buildings occasionally. It is possible that lack of an articulated safety strategy could be part of the problem. One of the serious problems is finance; government financing as regards to safety systems in buildings in buildings (both public and private) is

minimal. The grant towards maintenance of infrastructural facilities is at its lowest ebb. Most buildings and infrastructures have been neglected by subsequent tenures of government while the private sectors; the individual property owners have little or nothing to contribute towards effective installation of safety devices in their buildings. Again, there is the possibility that some of the challenges could be inherent within the fabric of the building, thus making safety management difficult or costly or both. Whatever the challenges may be, the result is that scores of public buildings in Owerri are without adequate and proper safety equipment and devices. The effect of these on the quality of the urban environment is negative, and could impact overall well-being of the user population.

1.3 Aims

The aim of this study is to evaluate the level of safety devices in public buildings in Owerri, Nigeria in order to improve the quality of the urban environment and the overall well-being of the user population.

1.4 Objectives

- To identify the level of safety devices in public buildings.
- To evaluate the conditions of the available equipment.
- To know if the necessary devices needed to ensure the safety of public buildings are adequate
- To know if construction professional engages the services of safety professionals.

1.5 Research Question

The study will provide answer to the following question:

1. What are the levels of safety devices that are found in public buildings in Owerri?
2. What are the conditions of the available equipment?
3. Are the necessary devices needed to ensure safety in public buildings adequate?
4. Do the construction professional engage the services of the safety professional?

1.6 Justification of the Study

In this study, the source used is the primary data source for its analysis. The questionnaires will be the instrument used for the collection of the primary data for this study which will be distributed to the users of the building and shall be sent to the respondents working in the Owerri Capital Development Authority (OCDA) and the safety officials in charge of the selected public buildings.

1.7 The study area

This study was carried out in Imo state in Owerri north local government area. The building to be study are Imo state university library, Imo internal revenue service and cathol cathedral church Anglican communion

1.8 Scope of the study

This study will be mainly concerned with safety devices in public buildings in Owerri, the capital city of Imo state. There are numerous safety devices but this study will focus only on fire safety protections, communication systems (CCTV, digital signage, tactile surfaces), and access controls (doors, emergency exits etc.).

1.9 Significance of the Study

The study is basically focused on evaluation of safety devices in public buildings. The benefits that will accrue from this study are meant to enlighten both government and private individuals on the need for safety systems in buildings especially public buildings. Also, the paper will provide suggestions and ways in which an effective safety system can be established and managed to prevent occasional hazards caused by lack of safety devices.

1.10 Limitation of Study

The limitation of study is only concentrated on public buildings in Owerri Imo state. The evaluation of safety devices will be carried out using questionnaire as the instrument to determine the level of safety devices in public buildings in Owerri Imo state.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

A building is regarded as an enclosure or “envelope” designed and constructed to provide minimum level of comfort, and conveniences for man. Building provides safety, protects human inhabitants, animals and equipment from effects of weather, and gives internal comfort (Ogunoh,2014). This implies that the primary purpose of buildings is to provide occupants with conducive, safe, comfortable, healthy and secured indoor environment to carry out different kinds of activities ranging from work, study, leisure and family life to social interactions. In order to achieve this purpose, buildings are designed, planned, constructed and managed based on standards and specifications established by governments, professional bodies and experts who are supposed to have adequate knowledge of users’ needs and expectations. Studies such as Kaitilla, (1993); Ukoha and Beamish, 1997; Zeiler and Boxem, 2008; Meir, Garb, Jiao and Cicelsky, 2009; Eziyi, Akunnay, Albert and Dolapo (2013) have however shown that sometimes these standards and specifications do not conform to the changing needs and expectations of users; and thus, users are not always satisfied with the performance of their buildings. The main functional requirement of building is to ensure strength and stability, weather tightness, internal comfort level, optimum use of buildings and a longer serviceable life of buildings. This is only possible through undertaking of periodic and planned maintenance, at regular intervals (Gahlot 2006). Aluga (2001) defines maintenance as work undertaken in order to keep or restore a facility at an acceptable standard. He further recommends that management should view building maintenance as part of its operating strategy for property preservation contributing to the success, well-being and operations of its occupants. He also confirms that proper maintenance contributes in ensuring safety of occupants, users of buildings and the public.

Siyanbola. Ogunmakinde and Akinola (2013) maintained that for proper maintenance of building it is necessary to conduct a condition survey. According to Watt (2009) building condition survey is a survey recording and documenting any damage (by a structural engineer) to the building structure - including superficial damage. It is done to track the occurrence or exacerbation of building damage over time to provide objective proof in the event of any damage claims.

Governments in the developed world have attempted to ensure adequate and quality building that is safe for their citizens considering the socio-economic importance of housing. For instance, the United Kingdom (UK) Government undertakes an investigation referred to as the English House Condition Survey every 5 years since 1967 to document the housing stock and monitor its changing condition to provide a basis for Government policies on home improvement, safety and area renewal. The survey entails physical examination of samples of housing stock, determination of history of repair and maintenance, inspection of installed safety devices and their interests in home improvement as well as ability to finance necessary work, determination of institutional contributions by local authorities in housing renewal and a survey of house values. It assisted in determining stock's need for repair, and what parts need repair, determining work force and resources required and proves whether maintenance and safety policies adopted are adequate.

The levels of defects and deteriorations in a building are the great influence to indicate the building performance instead of the services and safety systems provided. The interaction of both people and surroundings towards the life cycle of a building gives impact on the property values. Dealing with the sub-sale housing properties, calls for Valuers expertise, experience and knowledge in property valuation. It is understood that the scope of inspection is limited for the purpose of valuation only. Due to integration of skill and knowledge, the condition survey and assessment of building is foreseeable to help the Valuers in preparing an

accurate valuation for Sub-sale houses (Siyanbola *et al.* 2013). Despite the significance of buildings to economic development, the housing situation in Africa has greatly been influenced by implementation of structural adjustment programmer which recommended reduction of government expenditures for housing. The change in housing policy had far reaching effects in provision of housing for low-income earners in Africa. Subsequently, there has been minimal production of public housing for low income necessitating preservation of already existing housing stock (Ipingbemi, 2010).

Most buildings in Nigeria have suffered lack of maintenance and are prone to occurrence of accidents which is manifested in public buildings in all major urban centres in Nigeria, confirming declining investments in the maintenance of housing estates (Ipingbemi, 2010).

Building maintainability is defined in the British Standard Glossary of terms (BS 3811:1993), as a characteristic of design and installation, expressed when there is a high likelihood that an item will be retained in or restored to a specified condition following prescribed maintenance procedures. According to Feldman (1975), building maintainability is the condition of an item or a surface that permits its repair, adjustment or cleaning, with reasonable effort and cost. This suggests that an item or surface can be such that it may not be easy for maintenance activities to be effectively carried out on it, notwithstanding the desire to do so. The character of a surface or item that may permit ease of maintenance would clearly include location and placement of the item, and properties of the surface material, which are all outcomes of design. Chew and De Silva (2003) see building maintainability as achieving the optimum performance through the building life span within minimum cost. In this case, maintainability is achieved through use of durable safety devices and components, materials, and construction methods. Lau and Ho (2014) paint a more holistic picture of maintainability, covering both the character of the building and the maintenance strategy adopted in the building. They see building maintainability as features and/or measures that expedite

maintenance, leading to improved maintenance efficiency, augmented building performance and best value outcomes. The design component of maintainability is clearly stated in all the discourses. In summary, maintainability is a concept which addresses the need to improve effectiveness and efficiency of maintenance and safety (Rounds, 2018).

2.1.1 Safety Devices

Safety devices are pieces of equipment such as fire extinguishers, safety belts, burglar alarm, CCTV, digital signages, tactile surfaces etc.

Plate 2.1.1(a): Showing Examples of some safety devices

1. Fire extinguisher

A fire extinguisher is a handheld active fire protection device usually filled with a dry or wet chemical used to extinguish or control small fires, often in emergencies. It is not intended for

use on an out-of-control fire, such as one which has reached the ceiling, endangers the user (i.e., no escape route, smoke, explosion hazard, etc.), or otherwise requires the equipment, personnel, resources, and/or expertise of a fire brigade.

Type Extinguisher	Fire						Comments
	CLASS A Combustible materials (e.g. paper & wood)	CLASS B Flammable liquids (e.g. paint & petrol)	CLASS C Flammable gases (e.g. butane and methane)	CLASS D Flammable metals (e.g. lithium & potassium)	Electrical Electrical equipment (e.g. computers & generators)	CLASS F Deep fat fryers (e.g. chip pans)	
Water	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	Do not use on liquid or electric fires
Foam	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	Not suited to domestic use
Dry Powder	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	Can be used safely up to 1000 volts
CO2	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	Safe on both high and low voltage
Wet Chemical	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Use on extremely high temperatures

plate 2.1.1(b): showing Fire extinguisher types and uses for different classifications of fire

plate 2.1.1(c): Showing powder fire extinguisher

Standard dry powder fire extinguishers are also called ‘ABC’ extinguishers because they tackle class A, B and C fires, however, they are not recommended for use in enclosed spaces. This is because the powder can be easily inhaled, and also the residue is very difficult to clean up after. ABC powder extinguishers can also be used on some electrical fires. Specialist dry powder extinguishers are used for flammable metals.

2. Fire bucket

A Fire Bucket is filled with sand or water and is used to extinguish fires. Sand is often used where there is a risk of spilled flammable liquid which might ignite and spread by flowing across the ground. The sand is deployed to act as a barrier to the flowing liquid.

Water filled fire buckets are sometimes used where a water extinguisher might not be convenient, or where a supplement is prudent.

plate 2.1.1(d): Showing fire bucket

3. Security cameras

Security Camera means any item, system, camera, technology device, communications device, or process, used alone or in conjunction with a network, for the purpose of gathering, monitoring, recording or storing an image or images of District facilities and/or people in the district facilities. Such devices may include, but are not limited to: analog and digital Security cameras, closed circuit television, web cameras, and computerized visual monitoring.

plate 2.1.1(e): Showing security cameras

4. Smoke detectors

A smoke detector is a device that senses smoke, typically as an indicator of fire. Smoke detectors are usually housed in plastic enclosures, typically shaped like a disk about 150 millimeters (6 in) in diameter and 25 millimeters (1 in) thick, but shape and size vary. Smoke can be detected either optically (photoelectric) or by physical process (ionization). Detectors may use one or both sensing methods. Sensitive alarms can be used to detect and deter smoking in banned areas. Smoke detectors in large commercial and industrial buildings are usually connected to a central fire alarm system.

© 2004 Honeywell Corp.

plate 2.1.1(f): Showing smoke detector

5. Fire exit door

A Fire exit door is important for emergency exits in structures as it allows for faster evacuation in emergencies such as fire outbreak. Fire exit doors are made from heavy duty steel and they are all certified. These fire rated Emergency Exit Doors have hourly ratings of 90 minutes and 120 minutes (with glass) manufactured for our heavy-duty specification at 1.0M x 2.1M @ 450,000. Fire Exit doors are suitable for stairwells of commercial centers, offices, hotels and residential apartments.

plate 2.1.1(g): Showing fire exit door

6. Loudspeakers

An LRAD is a loudspeaker-like device that emits a focused beam of sound. What makes these systems unique is that rather than transmitting sound like a loudspeaker in many directions (similar to the way a lightbulb emits light), LRAD systems transmit sound in a narrow beam (much like a flashlight). It is used to pass information quickly to a large number of user population.

plate 2.1.1(h): Showing loudspeaker

7. Signages

The installation of safety signage is mandated by the health and safety at work act 1974. Safety signs must be provided and maintained in circumstances where a health and safety risk or hazards are identified.

Mandatory safety signs consist of:

Warning signs (warning of a hazard) – triangular signs with black pictogram and yellow background.

Prohibition signs (prohibits an action) – round shape with black or white pictogram and either red edgings or a diagonal line.

Mandatory action signs (prescribes specific behavior) – round shape with white pictogram and blue background.

Emergency signs (information for emergency situations) – rectangular or square shape with white pictogram and green background.

Fire safety signs (information for fire emergency) - combination of warning and emergency signs.

plate 2.1.1(i): Showing types of signages

8. Tactile surfaces

Tactile paving (also called tenji blocks, truncated domes, detectable warnings, tactile tiles, tactile ground surface indicators, tactile walking surface indicators, or detectable warning surfaces) is a system of textured ground surface indicators found on stairs and railway station platforms, to assist pedestrians who are vision impaired

plate 2.1.1(j): Showing tactile surfaces

Plate 2.1.1(k): Showing Building security and control systems.

2.1.2 Building Maintenance

Maintenance is the combination of all technical, administrative, and managerial actions during the lifecycle of an item intended to retain it in or restore it to a state in which it can perform the required function (BS EN 13306:2010). Building maintenance is necessary to sustain the utility value of a building (Plavina & Geipele, 2013). Maintenance operations in a building can be broadly categorized as routine, preventive and remedial maintenance. Regular cleaning and beautification of building and premises amount to routine maintenance, and are necessary to keep the structure functional and protected from early decay.

Preventive maintenance is all activities undertaken to keep the building structure sound and unsusceptible to early damage. Remedial maintenance on the other hand, are measures undertaken to correct, remove or repair a damaged part of a building. The frequency and cost layout of these maintenance activities largely depend on the building itself, and the maintenance strategy adopted.

2.1.3 Maintainability and Safety of public buildings

Public buildings by their sheer size and function, are prominent fixtures in any urban environment. These buildings do not exist in isolation. They are a part of the whole town or city, and together with physical infrastructure and spaces, define the design of the urban space. It is known that urban design features can enhance the quality of life in the built environment (CABE, 2002). Urban quality of life according to McCrea et al (2005) includes satisfaction at regional, neighborhood, and housing levels. While regional satisfaction is concerned with services like health, education, cost of living, and urban growth, neighborhood satisfaction is best predicted by evaluations of social interactions and quality of public facilities.

Quality of public facilities is particularly important because it has been shown to have implications for effective administration of public services, with attendant effects on crime, health, safety, and social behaviour (Deniz, 2016; Rastyapina and Korosteleva, 2016). Urban quality of life does not only refer to the quality of life in urban areas as conventionally known, but also to the quality of its built environment (El Din et al, 2013; Garau and Pavan, 2018). Keeping the built environment in good condition is therefore a key component in ensuring improved quality of urban life.

Public buildings by virtue of their character entertain large numbers of users from varying backgrounds, and thus face peculiar issues relating to operation and maintenance. In Nigeria, maintenance of existing infrastructure is not given the prime of place accorded to new construction (Odediran et al., 2012 in Ofori, Duodu and Bonney, 2015). As a result, the process of decay and dilapidation of public buildings starts quite early in the life of the buildings. The economic and environmental fallouts as a result of this, greatly impinge on the sustainable development of cities and communities. To retain economic value, the buildings must be maintained in a cost-effective way and must contain adequate and up-to-date safety evinces installed in them. Accordingly, the concept of safety in public buildings becomes relevant in terms of minimizing the costs and resources required for buildings to function effectively throughout their life span (Government of Singapore, 2016).

2.2 Empirical Framework

In recent years, not much has happened to transform this scenario requiring the relevant actors to conserve these assets for purposes of prosperity and posterity. Waziri and Vanduhe (2013) in their study titled “evaluation of factors affecting residential building maintenance in Nigeria” confirm that the country has had challenges of planning, development and management of its residential neighborhoods. This has resulted in deterioration of

surrounding buildings and services due to lack of maintenance and the frequent occurrence of accidents which could have been prevented if there were safety devices installed in those buildings. Also, unattended wear and tear caused by negligence by local authorities and government agencies responsible for management of the built environment (Cobbinah, 2010). There are so many problems associated with the maintenance and safety of buildings and infrastructural facilities in the country. One of the serious problems is finance; government financing as regards to maintenance of buildings (both public and private) and installation of safety devices is minimal. The grant towards maintenance of infrastructural facilities is at its lowest ebb. Most buildings and infrastructures have been neglected by subsequent tenures of government while the private sectors; the individual property owners have little or nothing to contribute towards effective maintenance of their buildings. As long as the buildings afford the owner annual income, he would not care for the maintenance and so long the interior of the building is conducive for the occupants they could not care for outward appearance or other necessary maintenance activity. Another serious impediment to maintenance of building in Nigeria is the state of the economy, according to the United Nation research on profitability index as regards income per capita of nations of the world; Nigeria is rated as fifth poorest country (UN 2010), which implies that the average Nigerian lives below one dollar per day. Because of this economic hardship, residents and citizens have little or nothing to contribute in terms of effective maintenance of their abode thus leading to neglected effects visualized in our cities and metropolis. In addition, certain buildings in Nigerian cities were constructed during the pre-colonial era. Therefore, most of these buildings are aged due to wear and tear, weathering and climatic factors over the years thus resulting in dilapidated nature, which might not respond positively to modern day safety and maintenance techniques. The reason for this assertion being 51% repair replacement strategy, such buildings, the cost of their repairs might equal over 50% cost of new construction.

Buildings and infrastructural decay also stem from poor workmanship and poor supervision (Amobi, 2011). Most of these defects arise from the fact that the skill employed during the production of the buildings are defective, the supervision most times is minimal or left in the hands of unskilled foremen. Thus, creating a chance, which were filled by unprofessional ethics thus resulting in failure in the life of the structure and will eventually be translated to the overall life span of the building/structure.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Preview

The section of this study highlights the methodologies utilized in this study. It focuses on the research methodology used to study safety devices in public buildings, describing the population, determination of sample size, the various ways by which the respondents of the study were selected data analysis, and ethical issues related to data collection.

3.2 Research Design

Research design includes the processes utilized by the researcher in carrying out the study in order to answer the research questions and meet its objectives of the study, (Kumar, 2018). It is a framework that shows how the researcher conducted the research in order to obtain relevant data that matches the research objectives, (Crowl 1993). This present study adopts a descriptive research design through cross-sectional survey analysis; the justification for this design is that it studies individual attitude and belief within a certain period of time, (Crowl 1993). This is effective in studies that seek to establish the current status of existing phenomena without interference. Data collection was through survey. The study used the descriptive survey to define and examine associative differences and relationships. This method provides useful and accurate information that answers questions regarding who, what, when and how (Kombo & Tromp, 2006).

- The first step in carrying out this research would be identifying the research problems, issues and scope of research. The selected study is selected after choosing three case study. The research of this study will then have established, the results out come with four strong objectives which is to identify the level of safety devices in public buildings.

- To evaluate the conditions of the available equipment.
- To know if the necessary devices needed to ensure the safety of public buildings are adequate.
- To know if construction professional engages the services of safety professionals.

3.3 Sampling

The case of this research will be conducted at buildings in Owerri north local government area selected for this research. The selected case study would be the Imo state university library, the Imo state internal revenue service and catol cathedral church Anglican communion. The investigation of this research will depend of the users of the building and the basic questions will be answering What are the levels of safety devices that are found in public buildings in Owerri, what are the conditions of the available equipment, what are the necessary devices needed to ensure safety in public buildings and Do the construction professional engage the services of the safety professional. All this question will influence how the data will be collected.

3.3.1 Population

A population can be defined as the complete set of subjects that can be studied: people, objects, animals, plants, organizations from which a sample may be obtained (Shao, 1999). Shao, (1999) describe population as the entire group or set of cases that a researcher is interested in generalizing. The population of this study involve three buildings, each chosen from education, civic and religious buildings. because they are the predominant public building types in the study area.

The selection of the case studies is determined by the scope of area which is Owerri north local government area. The choosing buildings were;

- Imo state university library.
- Imo state internal revenue service.
- Catol cathedral church Anglican communion.

Building type	buildings	Number of spaces
Institutional	Imo state university library	10
Institutional	Imo state internal revenue service	12
Institutional	Catol cathedral church Anglican communion	3

Table 3.3.1 showing the building type and number of spaces

3.3.2 Sampling frame

The range at which this study is carried out in the public buildings at Owerri north local government area. The buildings are; Imo State university library is a one-story building with two reading halls, a book store space and a user store space is located in the ground floor while the second floor accommodates the office spaces. Imo state internal revenue service (office building) accommodating twelve offices, six offices in each floor. Catol cathedral church Anglican communion accommodating a large nave for worshipers, a sacristy and a second hall for other church activities.

3.3.3 Sampling Method

The sampling method utilized is the probability sampling technique. This is because the technique makes use of randomization to make sure that every element involved in the population gets an equal chance to be part of the selected sample. A sub-type of probability sampling is the stratified sampling. This method of sampling divides the elements within the group into strata based on the similarity in such a way that the elements within the group are homogenous and heterogenous among the other subgroups formed.

3.3.4 Sampling Size

The measure of the number of individual samples used in the survey is 50. The number of questionnaires handed out was 50. 42 were returned.

3.4 Methods of Data collection

A combination of both qualitative and quantitative method was used in this study. The study involved observation, questionnaires and analysis of responses. The data needed for the study will be gotten based on the questions provided in the questionnaire. The data will focus mostly on the level of safety equipment, conditions of safety equipment, necessary devices involved and whether the construction professional involved the services of a safety equipment expert. The questionnaire consists of two sections which is section A and B. Section A contained the demographics of the respondents while section B contained the questions to be answered by the respondents.

3.5 Area of Study

The study area covered the core administrative zone of Owerri capital territory, which is Owerri north local government areas. Owerri is the capital city of Imo state in southeast Nigeria. It is also a growing center of entertainment, attracting visitors from neighboring states to its hotels, bars, restaurants, and night clubs. Good public infrastructure would substantially enhance the status of the city, and support its continued growth. The institutional building type was selected for this survey, consisting of the educational, civil and religious building. These make up the majority of public building typology in Owerri. Fifty copies of questionnaire were administered in fifty separate buildings falling into these four categories.

Source: author (2022)

Plate 3.5: Showing map of Imo state indicating Owerri north

3.6 Data Collection and processing

This study made use of primary data for its analysis. The questionnaires shall be the instrument used for the collection of the primary data for this study and it shall be sent to the respondents working in the Owerri Capital Development Authority (OCDA) and the safety officials in charge of the selected public buildings.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

The study shall use two phases of analysis for data analysis: the descriptive and the inferential analysis. Preliminary use of Microsoft Excel shall be employed to clean up and normalize the collected data before the detailed process of cleaning in SPSS. In order to illustrate variations in response and viewpoints the descriptive study for the first stage shall use denotations and frequencies and other descriptive elements, with the help of SPSS software.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Preview

In this chapter, the data from the study were referred to objectives which are to identify, the level of safety devices in public buildings, to evaluate the conditions of the available equipment, to know if the necessary devices needed to ensure the safety of public buildings are adequate and To know if construction professional engage the services of safety professionals collated, presented and discussed. The researcher presented the data in line with

Location map of the study area

Source: author (2022)

Plate 4.0: Showing location of the study area circled in red as indicated.

4.1 Data on Imo state university library

Plate 4.1(a): Showing Imo state university library

4.1.1 Equipment available in the building

s/n	Safety devices	No. Available
1	Fire extinguisher	4
2	Fire bucket	12
3	Security cameras	0
4	Smoke detectors	0
5	Emergency exit doors	1
6	loudspeakers	0
7	signages	0
8	Tactile surfaces	0

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.1.1 showing equipment available in the building.

Statistics

No. Available

N	Valid	8
	Missing	0
Mean		2.13
Median		.00
Std. Deviation		4.224

		No. Available			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	0	5	62.5	62.5	62.5
	1	1	12.5	12.5	75.0
	4	1	12.5	12.5	87.5
	12	1	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	8	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.1.1(a): Showing equipment available in the building

Figure 4.1.1(b): Showing equipment available in the building

4.1.2 Conditions of the Available Equipment

The safety devices present within the building consist of both the ones in the working condition as well as does that are not functioning.

s/n	Building floors	Activities	Devices Available	No. Working	No. not Working	Total
1	Ground floor	Reading hall and offices	Fire extinguisher	1	1	2
2	Ground floor	Circulation lobby	Fire bucket	2	4	6
1	First floor	offices	Fire extinguisher	1	1	2
1	First floor	Circulation lobby	Fire bucket	1	5	6

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.1.2 showing condition of available equipment.

Plate 4.1.2(a): Showing Imo state university library

Plate 4.1.2(b): Showing Imo state university library

4.2 Data on Imo state internal revenue service

Plate 4.2: Showing Imo internal revenue service

4.2.1 Equipment available in the building

s/n	Safety devices	No. Available
1	Fire extinguisher	4
2	Fire bucket	0
3	Security cameras	6
4	Smoke detectors	0
5	Emergency exit doors	1
6	loudspeakers	0
7	signages	0
8	Tactile surfaces	0

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.2.1 showing equipment available in the building.

Statistics

No.Available

N	Valid	8
	Missing	0

		No.Available			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	0	5	62.5	62.5	62.5
	1	1	12.5	12.5	75.0
	4	1	12.5	12.5	87.5
	6	1	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	8	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.2.1(a): Showing equipment available in the building

Figure 4.2.1(b): Showing equipment available in the building

4.2.2 Conditions of the Available Equipment

The safety devices present within the building consist of both the ones in the working condition as well as does that are not functioning.

s/n	Building floors	Activities	Devices Available	No. Working	No. not Working	Total
1	Ground floor	offices	Fire extinguisher	1	1	2
2	Ground floor	Circulation lobby	Security cameras	3	0	3
1	First floor	offices	Fire extinguisher	1	1	2
1	First floor	Circulation lobby	Security cameras	2	1	3

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.2.2 showing condition of available equipment.

Plate 4.2.2(a): Showing Imo state internal revenue service

Plate 4.2.2(b): Showing Imo state internal revenue service

4.3 Data on catol cathedral church Anglican communion

Plate 4.3: Showing catol cathedral church Anglican communion.

4.3.1 Equipment available in the building

s/n	Safety devices	No. Available
1	Fire extinguisher	1
2	Fire bucket	6
3	Security cameras	0
4	Smoke detectors	0
5	Emergency exit doors	2
6	loudspeakers	0
7	signages	6
8	Tactile surfaces	0

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.3.1 showing equipment available in the building.

Statistics

No.Available

N	Valid	8
	Missing	0

		No.Available			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	0	4	50.0	50.0	50.0
	1	1	12.5	12.5	62.5
	2	1	12.5	12.5	75.0
	6	2	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	8	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.3.1(a): Showing equipment available in the building

Figure 4.3.1(b): Showing equipment available in the building

4.3.2 Conditions of the Available Equipment

The safety devices present within the building consist of both the ones in the working condition as well as does that are not functioning.

s/n	Building floors	Activities	Devices Available	No. Working	No. not Working	Total
1	Ground floor	sacristy	Fire extinguisher	1	0	1
2	Ground floor	Entrance concourse	Fire bucket	4	2	6
1	Ground floor	Emergency exit	Emergency door	2	0	2

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.3.2 showing condition of available equipment.

Plate 4.3.2(a): Showing catol cathedral church Anglican communion.

Plate 4.3.2(b): Showing catol cathedral church Anglican communion.

4.4 Research Question I

What are the levels of safety devices found in public buildings in Owerri?

S/N	ITEMS	VERY HIGH	HIGH	FAIR	POOR	VERY POOR
1	What is the quality of safety devices found in public buildings in Owerri	5	10	20	5	2
2	What is the level of maintenance of such safety devices	4	8	18	8	4
3	To what extent does safety devices help in increasing the longevity of public buildings	25	10	4	2	1
4	What is the extent gone in ensuring the availability and insistence of safety devices in public buildings?	7	8	11	10	6

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.4: Showing the results and responses on the level of safety devices in Owerri.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
VERY HIGH	4	4	25	10.25	9.912
HIGH	4	8	10	9.00	1.155
FAIR	4	4	20	13.25	7.274
POOR	4	2	10	6.25	3.500
VERY POOR	4	1	6	3.25	2.217
Valid N (listwise)	4				

Source: SPSS version 26

ITEMS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	To what extent does safety devices help in increasing the longevity of public buildings	1	25.0	25.0	25.0
	What is the extent gone in ensuring the availability and insistence of safety devices in public buildings?	1	25.0	25.0	50.0
	What is the level of maintenance of such safety devices	1	25.0	25.0	75.0
	What is the quality of safety devices found in public buildings in Owerri	1	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	4	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS version 26

Figure 4.4: Showing the results and responses on the level of safety devices in Owerri.

The data above showed the percentage responses of the respondents on the level of safety devices. Following the table was the analysis of the responses using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 26. The Table showed that 5 out of 42 people rated the quality of

safety devices in the selected public buildings found very high. 10 rated it high and 20 people were of the opinion that it was fair. 5 persons were of the view that it was poor while 2 people rated the quality of safety devices in the selected public buildings were very poor. As regards to the level of maintenance of safety devices, 4 people were of the opinion that it was very high, 8 said it was high, 18, 8 and 4 persons said it was fair, poor and very poor respectively. 25 persons noted that what extent at which safety devices help in increasing the longevity of public buildings is very high. 10 people said it was high, 4 people – fair, 2-poor, 1-very poor. In insisting on the proper and adequate installation and use of safety devices in public buildings, 7 people said that it was on a very high extent, 8 people said it was on a high extent, 11 people were of the opinion that it was fair, 10 people said it was poor and 6 people said it was very poor.

4.5 Research Question 2

What are the conditions of the safety equipment in the buildings?

S/N	ITEMS	VERY GOOD	GOOD	FAIR	POOR	VERY POOR
1	What are the conditions of the safety equipments in the buildings	15	15	8	2	2

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.5: Showing conditions of the safety equipment in the building.

Statistics

What are the conditions of the safety devices

N	Valid	6
	Missing	0

What are the conditions of the safety devices

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15	2	33.3	33.3	33.3
	2	2	33.3	33.3	66.7
	8	1	16.7	16.7	83.3
	What are the conditions of the safety devices	1	16.7	16.7	100.0
Total		6	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.5(a): Showing conditions of the safety equipment in the building.

Figure 4.5(b): Showing conditions of the safety equipment in the building.

As can be observed from the analysis, 15 people were of the opinion that the conditions of safety devices found in the buildings were very good, 15 people said it was good, 8 people were of the view that it was fair, 2 people thought the conditions of the safety devices are poor, while 2 people were of the opinion that it was very poor.

4.6 Research Question 3

Are the necessary devices needed to ensure safety in public buildings adequate?

S/N	ITEMS	VERY ADEQUATE	ADEQUATE	MILDLY ADEQUATE	POORLY ADEQUATE	VERY POORLY ADEQUATE
1	Are the necessary devices needed to ensure safety in public buildings adequate?	16	12	7	4	3

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.6: Showing the results and responses on the adequacy of the necessary devices.

Statistics

Are the necessary devices needed to ensure safety of the public buildings adequate?

N	Valid	6
	Missing	0

Are the necessary devices needed to ensure safety of the public buildings adequate?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	12	1	16.7	16.7	16.7
	16	1	16.7	16.7	33.3
	3	1	16.7	16.7	50.0
	4	1	16.7	16.7	66.7
	7	1	16.7	16.7	83.3
	Are the necessary devices needed to ensure safety of the public buildings adequate?	1	16.7	16.7	100.0
Total		6	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.6(a): Showing the results and responses on the adequacy of the necessary devices.

Figure 4.6(b): Showing the results and responses on the adequacy of the necessary devices.

As can be observed from the analysis, 12 people were of the opinion that the necessary devices needed to ensure safety of public buildings are very adequate, 16 people were of the view that it was adequate, 3 people were of the view that it was mildly adequate, 4 people felt it was poorly adequate, while 7 people said they were very poorly adequate.

4.7 Research Question 4

Do the construction experts involve the services of safety professionals?

S/N	ITEMS	YES	NO
	Do the construction experts involve the services of safety professionals?	33	9

Source: Field Survey 2022.

Table 4.7: Showing the results and responses on the construction experts involving the services of the professionals.

Statistics

Does the construction expert engage the services of a safety equipment expert?

N	Valid	2
	Missing	4
Mean		21.00
Std. Deviation		16.971
Minimum		9
Maximum		33

Does the construction expert engage the services of a safety equipment expert?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	9	1	16.7	50.0	50.0
	33	1	16.7	50.0	100.0
	Total	2	33.3	100.0	
Missing	System	4	66.7		
Total		6	100.0		

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Does the construction expert engage the services of a safety equipment expert?	2	9	33	21.00	16.971
Valid N (listwise)	2				

Figure 4.7(a): Showing the results and responses on the construction experts involving the services of the professionals.

Figure 4.7(b): Showing the results and responses on the construction experts involving the services of the professionals.

When asked if the construction expert engages the services of a safety equipment expert, 33 people answered Yes. While only 9 people answered No.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND SUMMARY OF THE STUDY

Preview

In this chapter, the following subheadings will be outlined or reviewed; discussion of findings, implications of the study, limitations of the study, conclusion and summary and recommendations.

5.1 Discussion of Findings

The descriptive data presented in the table indicated the level of safety devices in public buildings as identified by their mean scores. Overall, very high, high, fair, poor and very poor had mean scores of 10.25 9.00 13.25 6.25 3.25 respectively. It can be deduced from this that a greater number of the respondents were of the opinion that the level of safety devices in public buildings in Owerri were fair. The extent at which safety devices help in increasing the longevity of public buildings had a cumulative percentage of 25, while the extent gone in ensuring the availability and insistence of safety devices in public buildings had a cumulative percentage of 50, with the level of maintenance of such safety devices having the cumulative frequency of 75 and the quality of safety devices found in public buildings in Owerri – 100 percent cumulative frequency. This means that level of safety devices in public buildings in Owerri were to an extent fair or adequate. This is not in line with the findings of Okpoechi & Nwankwo (2018) whose findings showed a high prevalence of defects in all component parts of public buildings studied in Owerri. The defects were observed regardless of building function, usage, safety devices, design, or construction method. As for research question 2, 15 people were of the opinion that the conditions of safety devices found in the buildings were very good, 15 people said it was good, 8 people were of the view that it was fair, 2 people thought the conditions of the safety devices are poor, while 2 people were of the

opinion that it was very poor. Research question three tried to determine if the necessary safety devices needed to ensure the safety of public buildings are adequate. From our findings it was revealed that 12 people were of the opinion that the necessary devices needed to ensure safety of public buildings are very adequate, 16 people were of the view that it was adequate, 3 people were of the view that it was mildly adequate, 4 people felt it was poorly adequate, while 7 people said they were very poorly adequate. Research question four bordered on whether the construction experts engaged the services of safety experts when handling the construction of a building and it from our findings when asked if the construction expert engages the services of a safety equipment expert, 33 people answered Yes. While only 9 people answered No.

5.2 Implications

It has been discovered that safety devices are very important in public buildings. It implies that public buildings should endeavor to have installed safety devices in order to prevent avoidable accidents and harm on people. During the construction, the appropriate materials should be used for the construction of buildings and adequate and easy to access safety devices should be installed.

5.3 Limitations of the study

1. Since this study is survey research, it was limited to a small sample size and may likely affect the generalization of results.
2. The study was limited to public buildings in Imo State but incorporating other states would have yielded more broader findings.

3. The statistical tool used in the study was limited because it made use of the questionnaire but the inclusion of interview and other instruments for data collection would have yielded broader findings.

5.4 Conclusion and Summary of the study

Designing for maintainability simply means designing to make for easier and more cost-effective maintenance of the designed feature. The study established those public buildings in Owerri have high a fair amount of safety devices installed in them. This should be encouraged to boost to the corporate image of the city, especially in the light of the role of public buildings as critical indicators of the quality of life of the people who use and own them. This suggests that currently, the aspects of design in public buildings, which would significantly improve their maintainability have not been fully explored, as poorly maintained public buildings span across the different building types, irrespective of usage and function. Conclusions of this study point to the fact that emphasis in design of public buildings should be placed on durability and safety which would be achieved by installing safety devices. Durability is that quality of materials and components to be strong, last for long periods, and resist stress and force, while still retaining aesthetic and functional value while safety is that all devices required for safety be installed. Space planning, construction detailing, materials specification, and production of maintenance manual must be done with the aim of achieving durability. Designing for durability and safety will keep the appeal of public buildings for prolonged periods of time even in the absence of preventive maintenance. This would also effectively minimize the cost and resources required for the buildings to function effectively. The services of safety experts should be engaged by construction engineers to bring in their knowledge as to what safety devices to install, how much of it that would be in pace and the steps to take in maintaining and taking care of them.

5.5 Recommendations

- 1) Buildings should be properly oriented before design
- 2) Fire escapes and other alternatives to leaving the building in case of any emergency should never be left out in any public building.
- 3) Safety devices should be effectively and adequately installed.
- 4) Architects should apply effective design strategies in their designs so as to integrate safety devices in the buildings, both manual and automatic.
- 5) Maintenance of safety devices should be encouraged

5.6 Suggestions for Further Studies

For the purpose of solving architectural problems, the researcher suggests that this study should be carried out in residential and public buildings of other states rather than only Imo.

References

- Aluga, O. T. (2001). Impact of sustainability of building maintenance practices of local council buildings on performance of floor finishes. Unpublished project work.
- Amobi C. O. (2011). *Building Surveying Practice and Maintenance Management*. Achugo Publications, Owerri.
- Amobi, C. O. (2006). *Fundamentals of Building Maintenance Technology and Management*. Achugo Publications, Owerri.
- British Standards Institution (1993) British Standard Glossary of Terms in Terotechnology BS 3811:1993, London: Bromilow
- British Standards Institution (2010) British Standard on Maintenance Terminology BS EN 13306:2010
- Che-Ani A. I., Ramly, A., Zain, M.F.M., Tawil, N.M., Hashim, A.E (2008a). "Assessing the condition of traditional Khmer timber houses in Cambodia: A priority ranking approach". *Journal of Building Appraisal* 4(2), 87-102.
- Che-Ani. A. I. (2008b). Role and methods of building defects inspection. Building maintenance course. Cambodia: Building Inspection Technology & Performance Monitoring. Building & Urban Dev. Inst (BUDI).
- Chew, M. and De Silva, N. (2003) 'Maintainability risks of condominiums in Sri Lanka', *Building Research and Information*, 3(1), pp. 60-69
- Commission for Architecture and Built Environment CABE (2002) The Value of Good Design [online] Available at: <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/sites/default/files/asset/document/the-value-of-good-design.pdf> (Accessed 18th February 2019)

- Couch, C. and Dennemann, A. (2000) 'Urban Regeneration and Sustainable Development in Britain: The example of the Liverpool ropewalks partnership' *Cities*, 17 (2), pp.137-147
- Crowl, T. K. (1993). *Qualitative Research Methods*. In P. Geller & S. Schmidt (Eds.). *Fundamentals of Educational Research* (pp. 432-456). Dubuque, IA: Brown and Benchmark
- Deniz, D. (2016) 'Improving perceived safety for public health through sustainable development' *Procedia – Social and Behavioural Sciences* 216 pp. 632 – 642
- Department of Culture Media and Sport (2000) *Better public buildings- a proud legacy for the future*, London: Department of Culture Media and Sport
- Egan, J. (2010) *Accelerating Change*, A report by the strategic forum for construction El Din, H. S.; Shalaby, A.; Farouk, H. E.; Elariane, S. A. (2013) 'Principles of urban quality of life for a neighbourhood' *Housing and Building National Research Centre* vol 9, no 1, pp. 86-92 [online] Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hbrcj.2013.02.007> (Accessed 2nd February 2019)
- Federal Government of Nigeria (2003) *National Insurance Act 2003* [online] <https://nass.gov.ng/document/download/5813>
- Feldman, E. B. (1975) *Building Design for Maintainability*, New York: McGraw-Hill
- Garau, C. and Pavan, V. M. (2018) 'Evaluating urban quality : Indicators and assessment tools for smart sustainable cities' *Sustainability* 10, 575; <https://doi:10.3390/su10030575> (Accessed 5th June 2019)
- Government of Singapore (2016) *Design for Maintainability Checklist* [online] Available at: https://www.bca.gov.sg/performanceBased/others/DM_checklist_2016.pdf (Accessed 18th February 2019)

- Ikpo, I.J. (2009) 'Maintainability indices for public building design' *Journal of Building Appraisal*, 4(4) pp. 321-327
- Ipingbemi, O. (2010). *Facility Management Unpublished Msc Housing Development and Management Lecture Notes*. University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Latham, M. (1994) *Constructing the Team, Final report of joint review of procurement and contractual agreements in the United Kingdom Construction Industry*, London, UK
- Okpoechi, .C. and Nwankwo, .S. (2019). "Improving maintainability of public buildings in Owerri Nigeria". *West Africa Built Environment Research (WABER) Conference 10th Anniversary Conference, 5-7 August 2019, Accra, Ghana Proceedings Edited by Laryea, S. and Essah, E. ISBN: 978 – 9988 – 2– 6010 – 1*
- Osuagwu et al (2020). "Current Issues Associated With Public Building Maintenance in South-East Nigeria". *IJISSET - International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, Vol. 8 Issue 2, February 2021
- ISSN (Online) 2348 – 7968 | Impact Factor (2020) – 6.7**